

Development of a blockchain-based marketplace for the Internet of Things data

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is recognised as a game-changer technology that expands its applicability to a huge variety of domains. The key asset is the data that the myriad of sensors embedded in the environment are constantly generating. The paper describes a Blockchain-based IoT Data Marketplace (BIDM) and presents the proof-of-concept implementation that has been developed to validate it from a functional standpoint. The BIDM enables an ecosystem where sensor owners can expose the observations that their sensors generate while retaining control over who accesses each observation and directly getting revenues according to the price they have set.

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1. Introduction

IoT solutions' landscape is still largely fragmented, with vertical platforms dominating and horizontal standards more mirroring experimental petri dishes rather than solutions to real problems [1,2]. Thus, a major challenge for IoT that is not already sufficiently addressed is the siloed approach used in most of the scenarios. The owner of the deployment is, at the same time, the service provider and the service consumer. It is hard to find IoT platforms that allow the exchange of data generated by heterogeneous providers and demanded by heterogeneous consumers. This results in below-critical mass efforts in standardisation and commodity solutions. Vendor lock-in thus dictates the landscape, resulting in lowering users' confidence that smartization strategies can achieve a major change [3]. Conversely, the fragmentation of emerging IoT-enabled platforms makes it difficult for entrepreneurs and SMEs, which fears platform lock-in, to achieve economies of scale by replicating innovative solutions from one scenario to another, even in the same application domain [4].

Additionally, from a security standpoint, data is, in most cases, only shared if not considered sensitive, and the success of services developed on top is often only modest [5]. A lot of data is still not shared because their owners, while conscious that it would be appreciated by potential consumers, do not have the skills to become themselves data providers. Additionally, they are not confident on how third parties that own IoT platforms with the capacity to export their data might use and deal with their data. IoT-generated data has the potential to offer higher value for richer smart services, but are not released for exploitation or not readily available. There is a lack of incentives, market confidence and trust for organisations and individuals to share new datasets as licensing models are not yet properly understood and developed, and key ecosystem foundation for such a marketplace is still missing. It is necessary to develop a secure-by-design approach increasing the transparency of all the IoT assets governance flow shifting from the current paradigm of discrete centralised trusted authorities to a paradigm of liquid and decentralised trust of the network as a whole.

Thus, there is a need for overcoming these major hurdles. On the one hand, we must avoid lock-in situations in which any of the ecosystem's stakeholders could gain a force position and discourage the rest. On the other hand, we must establish the mechanisms to promote an ecosystem in which as many as possible relevant actors are attracted.

To enable this scenario, it is necessary to set up a platform that allows the design and implementation of novel services and, why not, so-called killer applications. For the platform

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to be valuable, it has to be fed by as many assets, and the information that they generate, as possible. Moreover, it is of utmost importance to scale up the concept and federate such platform with different application domains so that the creative process can be enriched and its impact enlarged. Another crucial aspect that has been highlighted is the need to include enablers associated to the incentives and rewards of participating, not only during the trial phases but also considering the long-term sustainability of the whole platform and IoT ecosystem [6].

In this shift, the creation of Blockchain (BC) platforms that can be employed following the “as a Service” paradigm will enable fully decentralised solutions delivering certified mechanisms to support the management of IoT devices, during their whole lifecycle. Blockchain-based distributed ledger concept offers provenance and quality of data guarantee, as well as reputation mechanisms for qualification of shared assets. The shifting from the current paradigm of discrete centralised trusted authorities to a paradigm of decentralised trust of the web as a whole, responds to the consumers’ needs and to the providers’ demands. The first because they require reassurance of the data’s quality. The latter because they are reluctant to share some datasets due to uncertainty of how and for what purposes the data is used.

This paper presents a Blockchain-based IoT Data Marketplace (BIDM) that aims at enabling a platform for secure and transparent exchange of data. The BIDM creates an ecosystem on which transactions of data can be supported, initially, establishing a price for each observation, but also with the possibility for extending the requirements to be fulfilled by the buyer (reputation, purpose, etc.) in order to actually have access to the observations. The key contribution of the paper is the design and specification of the BIDM. In this respect, the paper presents the key design considerations, the functional architecture of the platform behind the BIDM and the main procedures that will take place in it. Additionally, the paper describes the main characteristics of the platform that have been implemented and deployed as an instance of a fully functional BIDM. In order to validate this implementation, it has been integrated with a large-scale IoT testbed [7] so that its behaviour can be assessed under real-world conditions.

The remaining of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents related work in the fields of horizontal IoT platforms aiming at addressing heterogeneous data sources and integration of BC as a tool for guaranteeing IoT data transaction. The BIDM architecture design and the specification of its components is described in Section 3. Section 4 presents the details of the implementation that has been carried out and summarises the proof-of-concept validation that has been accomplished integrating the BIDM with a large-scale IoT testbed. Finally, the main conclusions of the paper are gathered in Section 5.

2. Related work

Understanding datasets and data-streams generated by IoT deployments as something that can be exchanged in a trade

arena is tightly related to the Sensing as a Service (SaaS) model [8] in which context information is served to the applications that need it using a service-oriented architecture. The functional architecture defined for these scenarios is divided in three main tiers: sensor data producers, service providers, and sensor data consumers. The BIDM is applicable to the actors involved in all these tiers, as it enables controlled trading of measurements between those that own the IoT infrastructure and expose context information through services (i.e. sensor data producers) and the applications that make smart use of such information (i.e. sensor data consumers).

In the past, organisations could transfer raw IoT data acquired by users or obtained from data brokers, to a cloud server. Though, this has triggered concerns with regard to user privacy. In [9] it is argued that a P2P-network-based data marketplace is a fairer approach as weighted against a platform where each transaction is proxied through a central server. Additionally, it avoids single point of failure. Their work, however, does not consider the scalability problem of storing all the data in the distributed ledger as the proposal presented in this paper does. Additionally, they do not make any consideration on the IoT technologies to be used for guaranteeing integration with actual IoT platforms.

Another aspect that has to be carefully considered for the deployment of distributed marketplaces where there is no central authority regulating all the transactions is the existence of a trust management model. While this trust model has not been part of our work, existing platforms could be directly integrated. For example, [10] or [11] discuss on the properties (e.g. security, accuracy, reliability, availability of data, etc.) that should be added to an IoT platform to consider the metadata that is intrinsic to guaranteeing the trust in the use of the context data stemming from such platforms. These properties, could be added as part of the information model that we are considering in the BIDM. Moreover, their work focuses on the trust on the data rather than on the trust among producers and consumers, which is the aspect that BIDM mainly addresses.

Looking at the works that have been exploring the integration of BC and IoT, recent literature reviews [12] have shown the growing interest in this approach. However, many of them, at least those with an actual implementation, focus on specific application domains [13,14], instead of proposing a horizontal solution as we are doing in this paper. Still, there are already some technical architectures for data marketplaces which are directly related to our work.

Firstly, the MARS platform [15] has an analogous objective to the BIDM’s one consisting on setting up a system to foster data producers to consider their data as a tradeable asset and make it available for getting revenues from it. The solution uses a central authority which intermediates in the data transactions in order to guarantee the necessary trust between the market actors. Thus, they proposed a kind of hybrid approach which we are also leveraging in the BIDM. However, BIDM uses the central broker only for data storage while the trust and transactions are supported using the distributed approach provided by the underlying BC mechanisms. Moreover, our solution also enables data-stream consumption.

In [16] a data marketplace implemented as a smart contract on Ethereum BC is proposed. The paper coins the Data-as-a-Contract concept which very much resembles our main approach but using a P2P solution (Swarm) for the distributed data storage. It is precisely in the storage part of the design where our solution mainly differs. In this sense, the solution proposed for the BIDM relies on the standardised FIWARE enablers, which increases the discoverability of the data and also smooths the adoption of this solution by already existing FIWARE-based IoT data producers [17].

3. IoT marketplace architecture

3.1. Key design considerations

The proposed platform aims to integrate BC technology within any IoT environment providing the means to enable IoT providers selling their measurements to those customers who are interested in acquiring them. The inherent properties of BC technology allow to guarantee the traceability of the measurements. Thus, ensuring the following key points: (1) Guarantee that data is provided by reliable IoT producers; (2) Guarantee that customers pay for the data in a specific instant of time; (3) Guarantee that customers receive the measurements that they had bought; and (4) Guarantee secure and authorised-only access to the data. By achieving these features, we can accomplish a transparent system for both customers and IoT infrastructures.

3.2. System functional architecture

Fig. 1 shows the functional architecture of the BIDM including the different elements that interact in it (i.e. Market, IoT infrastructure and clients). The different colours represent the domain to which each of the components that make up the platform belongs. The green-shadowed elements (e.g. Smart Contracts) are controlled by the owner of the platform, while the blue ones (e.g. IoT infrastructure) are owned by external entities. The rest of elements (i.e. uncoloured ones) can be either a private or public Proof-of-Authority (PoA) BC.

There are two entities that interact with the BIDM: IoT infrastructures and the customers. The first ones act as producers of information. They do not need any extra component to send the measurements to the marketplace. They only have to send the measurement in NGSIV2 format with some extra fields, which will be explained in the next section.

On the other hand, customers act as information consumers. They must have a BC node to interact with the platform and buy the different measurements available in it. Thus, they are able to see at any time the blocks inserted in the BC, and consequently observe the measurements stored in the platform and purchase them. Additionally, customers can have a GUI to facilitate the browsing and purchasing process.

The cornerstone that supports the marketplace is the BC. This is a PoA BC based on Ethereum, which can be private or public depending on the needs of the owner of the platform. It can be Ethereum or any other BC that uses Ethereum’s core (e.g. Quorum). We have opted for the use of a PoA BC because of the mainly asynchronous (i.e. event-based) nature of the IoT.

By using PoA instead of other consensus mechanisms such as PoW it is possible to fix the amount of time between two mined blocks. Thus, minimising the number of empty blocks in the BC. In addition to this, we think that the BC ought to be a permissioned BC in which all the BC nodes have the same level of trustworthiness. This allows eliminating the need for fees which add extra cost for the mining of blocks in the BC.

The marketplace is divided in two different parts, namely Market Producer Storefront and Market Data Persistence Access. These can be described as follows:

1. The Market Producer Storefront part is the core of the Market. This element listens to the measurements provided by the IoT infrastructure and stores the minimal information needed to retrieve their value in the BC. In addition, it sends the measurements plus its hash to the Market Data Persistence Access so they can be stored permanently. To do this, the Market Producer Storefront uses the hashes of the measurements as unique identifiers to find them in the BC and in the database. The Market Producer Storefront can be divided in two elements: Market API and Market BC Node.

(a) The Market API is a proxy between the IoT infrastructure and the rest of the platform. Its main goal is to listen to the measurements supplied by the IoT infrastructures, process them, store the minimal information to retrieve them in the BC and send them plus their hash to the Market Data Persistence Access. Furthermore, it is always listening, through the Market BC Node, to the purchases in the BC.

(b) The Market BC Node is supervised by the owner of the platform. This element is used to insert content in the BC and to interact with the different smart contracts running on it.

2. The Market Data Persistence Access handles the storage of the measurements. In order to do this, it makes use of the FIWARE enablers: Orion Context Broker (OCB) and Cygnus, a MySQL database and a Measurements Broker. These elements can be described as follows:

(a) OCB is listening to the measurements provided by the Market API, which includes the measurement itself and its

Fig. 1. BIDM functional architecture.

hash, and sends them to those components that are subscribed to them. In this case, the only element subscribed to OCB is Cygnus. It is important to remark that the measurements do not come directly from the IoT infrastructure because the Market API has to generate their respective hashes and ensure that the information related to the measurements has been stored in the BC before sending them to OCB.

(b) Cygnus is the only consumer of the OCB. It translates the measurements coming from Orion in NGSIv2 format to SQL format and stores them in the MySQL database.

(c) The MySQL stores the measurements produced in the IoT infrastructures. Data stored is indexed by its hash.

(d) The Measurement Broker is responsible for retrieving the value of the measurements from the database whenever the Market API needs them.

Additionally, the platform employs three smart contracts running on the BC to work properly: Access Control, Data and Payment. These can be described as follows:

1. The Access Control smart contract is responsible for checking if an IoT producer is allowed to access to the platform. Furthermore, this smart contract also stores the clients' public keys to securely exchange the measurements purchased through the BC.

2. The Data smart contract stores all the information required to restore a measurement from the BC. To do so, this contract stores the hash of the measurement, the URL where the measurement is located and a brief description about the measurement. The last field is not essential. It is included to give customer a picture of what they are buying.

3. The Payment smart contract manages the purchases of the customers. When customers want to buy a measurement, it checks if they have already bought it or if they are in the process of buying it. This contract ensures that a client does not buy a measurement twice or buys the wrong measurement.

3.3. Market procedures

The platform supports two key procedures: the authentication of the IoT producers, and the purchase of measurements by customers.

3.3.1. Authentication of the IoT producers in the platform

To guarantee the provenance of the measurements inserted in the platform, only the IoT producers who have been previously authorised by the platform can interact with it. The process of authorisation consists on associating Ethereum accounts to unique identifiers (UID). Then, the platform assigns these identifiers along with the password to unlock the Ethereum account to the IoT infrastructures. This way, every producer registered in the platform has their own Ethereum account, so the platform can easily control who introduced the measurements by watching the account who produced the transaction in the BC. The procedure of giving the UIDs and the passwords to the IoT infrastructure is done out of the platform. Therefore, it will not be considered in this report.

The measurements sent by the IoT producers must include: the value of the measurement, their UID and their password

Fig. 2. Authentication procedure for IoT producers.

encrypted with the public key of the platform. Once the platform has received a measurement from the producer, it obtains the address associated to the UID and decrypts the password using its private key. If the password can unlock the Ethereum account then the producer has access to the platform and, thus, it can introduce new information in the Data smart contract. This procedure can be shown in Fig. 2.

This way, we have ensured that every measurement inserted in the platform comes from an authorised IoT producer. Thus, ensuring the reliable origin of the data.

3.3.2. Data purchase procedure

Fig. 3 shows the procedure that customers carry out to purchase measurements stored in the platform. Green steps are interaction with the BC without transactions (i.e. the reading of values from the BC), blue steps are interactions with the BC in the form of transactions (i.e. Purchase of the information) and colourless steps are HTTPS requests (i.e. retrieve the value of the measurements from the Measurements broker).

The steps that customers must follow are as follows:

1. Customers register their public key in the Access Control smart contract. This process is only carried out the first time that a client tries to purchase something of the platform.

2. A client (Client A) browses the different measurements published in the platform and decides to buy one (X). To initialise the purchase procedure, users produce a transaction to the Payment smart contract that triggers a purchase event.

3. The Market, which is always listening for the events produced in the Payment smart contract, observes the event triggered by A and extracts the hash of the measurement.

4. The Market uses the hash to obtain the URL of the measurement from the Data smart contract.

5. The Market obtains the value of the measurement by making a GET request to the URL just obtained.

6. The Market randomly generates a symmetric key and ciphers it with the public key of the client and with the public

Fig. 3. Data purchase procedure.

key of the admin user. Then, it sends a transaction to the client’s BC account with the encrypted symmetric key. The key is encrypted with both public keys to assure that the Market can prove that the data sent was the requested by the client.

7. The Market ciphers the measurement with the symmetric key generated in the previous step and sends it in a BC transaction to the client’s BC account. At this point, the clients have everything they need to recover the measurement. They only have to decrypt the symmetric key received in the previous step and use it to decrypt this transaction.

8. The Market emits an event in the Payment smart contract indicating the purchase of X by client A.

Client can check if the measurement that they have acquired is the one introduced by the IoT producer by comparing its hash with the one stored in the Data smart contract. By following the previous steps, it is possible to guarantee the traceability of the purchased measurements. This implies to know at every moment when a measurement has been bought and who has bought it.

4. Proof-of concept implementation and validation

4.1. Ecosystem deployment and marketplace components implementation details

For the proof-of-concept validation of the solution presented in this paper, all the components of the BIDM were implemented and integrated. All the components were deployed using Docker containers to facilitate replicability and extensibility of the system.

The core of the platform is the BC. In this respect, it was decided to use a private network implementing Ethereum Clique with PoA consensus algorithm implementation deployed in it. PoA is typically not considered suitable for public networks where the trust should be as distributed as possible. However, in our case permissioned control of the distributed network is part of the design considerations.

The BC network that was used during the functional validation tests was created with four nodes. Only two of them were sealers (the ones that seal/mine blocks). The other two are the interfaces for the Data Producer (Market BC Node) and the Consumer (Wallet BC node) respectively. These latter nodes have access to the BC but do not have rights to seal blocks (i.e. have read-only access to the BC). Additionally, a fifth node was deployed playing the role of a Bootnode. This

kind of nodes are used to bootstrap the P2P network discovery. While this might not be necessary for the reduced scale of the proof-of-concept validation scenario, it significantly reduces the neighbour discovery procedures in case of large networks. As the future lines of development and assessment of this solution target the scalability of the solution towards unrestricted number of Market and Wallet BC Nodes, the use of this kind of node was found adequate.

Regarding the smart contracts, they were implemented in Solidity and deployed directly to the BC. Upon registration of a node in the network, a copy of the contracts is immediately available so that data transactions can start upfront.

Finally, for the context management and data persistence, available Docker instances of the FIWARE OCB and Cygnus connector were deployed and configured. The OCB instance was configured to use MongoDB for data management while Cygnus was set up to store historical data within a MySQL.

4.2. Functional validation of the marketplace

The chosen scenario to perform the functional validation of the implemented BIDM was the IoT infrastructure of the city of Santander (SmartSantander). In this scenario, as can be shown in Fig. 4, the platform is subscribed to the SmartSantander platform (in this case implemented using the Orion Context Broker), thus it receives the measurements produced by the IoT sensors deployed in Santander.

On the other end of the system, to check the behaviour of the system, a client, whose sole purpose is to buy measurements produced in this environment, has been emulated. The client will browse the different measurements available in the platform and will buy some of them. To do so, the client uses a web server application that allows him to interact with the marketplace in an intuitive way.

The BC used is a private Ethereum BC with two validator nodes and a boot node. Aside from these, the platform and the client have their own non-validator nodes connected to the BC to interact with its content. Before starting on the marketplace and subscribing to SmartSantander’s OCB, we have generated an Ethereum account and we have assigned it to SmartSantander. Then, we have granted it enough privileges to insert measurements into the BC’s platform. This way, SmartSantander signs the blocks that contain its measurements and, therefore, it guarantees the provenance of the information.

The measurements sent by SmartSantander’s OCB are processed and stored in the platform so any client can buy them. The client can browse the different measurements stored in the

Fig. 4. Integration of the BIDM with Santander’s IoT infrastructure.

Data Available			
Latest 5 measurements			
Description	Publication Date	hash	Price
um.ngsi- Id:TrafficFlowObserved:santander.tr affic.flow:1022 by iot- smartsantander1	11:33:49 29-09-2020	0xaa6e48fa8acaba1a3eb61beca375 4fb3f179c4bde35d01b9aabc95131 38408	2
um.ngsi- Id:TrafficFlowObserved:santander.tr affic.flow:1021 by iot- smartsantander1	11:33:48 29-09-2020	0x8745166139b870ed6c6a3af8547 99a660e732ab84e31a50fd9f483a1b d7c524a	2
um.ngsi- Id:TrafficFlowObserved:santander.tr affic.flow:1019 by iot- smartsantander1	11:33:46 29-09-2020	0x0c9bb0664be071d639982b9b8d4 9c4c24c14b5aa1cf81c7de9366ac60 48695c6	2
um.ngsi- Id:TrafficFlowObserved:santander.tr affic.flow:1018 by iot- smartsantander1	11:33:45 29-09-2020	0xb31eb92211b0a89b42d13ccabd 30aae5a3818a4ff6f569d9bc99e19c6b cfecd4b	2
um.ngsi- Id:TrafficFlowObserved:santander.tr affic.flow:1017 by iot-	11:33:43 29-09-2020	0xc2c7177957771204d0c538b6679 7fd74cb13918bf8b05f9ded3cc74e 0a858	2

Fig. 5. Excerpt of data published in the platform.

platform through its web application. In Fig. 5, an example where several measurements stored in the platform is shown. The customer can check the time when the measurement was stored in the platform, its price and a brief description showing the purpose of the measurement, but he cannot check its value without purchasing it. In this example, all the measurements are produced by a set of sensors that measure the flow of traffic in different roads of Santander.

Customers can purchase the measurements in the Wallet tab. There, the client can buy new measurements and observe the value of the measurements that he had already bought. To check the value of a purchased measurement, the client just has to click over its hash (parameter that appears in blue). After clicking on the link, it emerges a new window that shows four parameters: the hash of the transaction that contains the symmetric key encrypted, the hash of the transaction that contains the encrypted measurement, the hash of the transaction that contains the hash of the measurement introduced in the BC and the plain value of the measurement.

The client can make sure that the purchased measurement is the one sent by the IoT infrastructure by hashing it and comparing the obtained hash with the hash that appears in the transaction that the IoT producer sent. Furthermore, the client can also check if the purchased measurement was produced by an authorised IoT producer by comparing the value of the address that originated that transaction with the ID associate to that address in the Access Control smart contract.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a platform that enable a decentralised marketplace, so-called Blockchain-based IoT Data Marketplace (BIDM), where information can be exchanged between IoT infrastructures generating it and applications exploiting it, in a fast, self-sovereign and totally transparent way. The solution proposed and described in the paper integrates standardised IoT ecosystems using the Connecting Europe's Facility Context-Broker (i.e. FIWARE OOCB) with BC technology to create an ecosystem on which transactions of data can be

supported, initially, establishing a price for each observation, but also with the possibility for extending the requirements to be fulfilled by the buyer (reputation, purpose, etc.) in order to actually have access to the observations. Furthermore, the use of this technology enables the traceability of the information, thus assuring at every moment who has bought a measurement and when. In addition, the authentication mechanism implemented in the platform guarantees the provenance of the data. Thus, providing reliability and quality to the platform.

To avoid the scalability problems associated with on-chain data storage, as other solutions have proposed, the BIDM keeps storage at specialised context and Big Data management enablers. This way, the process of synchronisation is significantly streamlined. Otherwise, it would be necessary to synchronise all the historical information which, for large IoT scenarios, could be a cumbersome process.

In this sense, the key contribution of the paper is the design and specification of the BIDM. In this respect, the paper presents the key design considerations observed, the functional architecture of the platform behind the BIDM and the main procedures that will take place, namely, the production and consumption of IoT-generated observations.

Additionally, the paper describes the key features of the platform that have been implemented as an instance of a fully functional BIDM. To validate this implementation, it has been integrated with a large-scale IoT testbed [8] so that its behaviour can be assessed under real-world conditions.

Future work will focus on two aspects, the implementation of a subscription system to acquire the measurements on the platform in an asynchronous and pseudo-real-time manner and the assessment of the scalability of the proposed solution in a larger pilot scenario including thousands of IoT devices producing measurements during a long period of time.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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